

Reimagining care for people living with diabetes in Norway: can lay health workers provide a more sustainable model?

Protocol: Development of a core outcome set

Introduction

Sustainability

UN worked out 17 sustainability goals with 169 targets as a part of the 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development (UN, 2023). Sustainability is thought to contain three dimensions consisting of economic (e.g. cost-effectiveness, resource distribution), social (e.g. equality and fairness) and environmental (e.g. reduce climate change, preserving nature), and means that we must develop and use what we need, but at the same time safeguard the resources for future generations (United Nations, 2023b)

Health care

The proportion of elderly people is increasing. It is estimated that during the next decades it will be more elderly people at the age of 65+ than young people (0-19 years) (Thomas, 2024). The consequences of an ageing population are many; there is the risk of multimorbidity, or non-communicable diseases, fertility rates decreases and there are less people in the global workforce, but more people requiring long-term care. This might lead to strain on the economy and health- and welfare systems (Knudsen, 2022; United Nations, 2023a). Though there is an increase in global health work force, many countries suffer from a lack of health personnel (United Nations, 2023a). In addition to undermining care provision for people with chronic conditions like diabetes, this workforce shortage is also recognized as a threat to the achievement of health-related sustainability goals (Farrenkopf & Lee, 2019; WHO, 2016).

As an example, in Norway the number of people living with diabetes is estimated to be around 270 000, in which approximately 23000 are living with diabetes mellitus type 1 (DM1) and the rest has diabetes mellitus type 2 (DM2) or other kinds of diabetes. DM1 is the most common form (Stene et al., 2021). Generally, the incidence of DM2 is rising

worldwide, and the chance of developing DM2 is increasing with age, though for the last decades also younger adults tends to develop this disease (Khan et al., 2020). While the cause of DM1 seems to be unclear, the cause of DM2 is typically caused by smoking, diet, obesity and physically inactivity (Stene et al., 2021). The consequences and complications of this chronic disease might be increased risk of cardiovascular diseases, peripheral neuropathy, foot ulcers, amputations, renal failures and hospitalizations (Alonso-Morán et al., 2014).

Lay health workers

Using lay health workers (LHW) can be a strategy to meet the challenges of the growing shortage of health professionals to deal with people with diabetes in primary health care. LHW can be defined as any health worker who is trained to perform functions related to health care delivery, but who does not have any formal training in health education. LHWs can be paid or voluntary, and they can be employed and led in organizations that may be public funded or be patient organizations (Lewin et al., 2005).

To be able to adopt LHW programmes for diabetes, the effect of the LHW programmes should be measurable. Clear and appropriate results, which are measured consistently, are essential for effective design and evaluation of health service interventions, as well as for decision-making in the health care system. Today, LHW programmes are assessed against a wide range of outcomes and using a diverse set of measures, with little consistency in relation to the assessed effects (Pantoja et al., 2022).

Why is it important to develop COS for diabetes and sustainability?

To our knowledge, there has not been any attempts to develop a core outcome set for LHW programmes for diabetes and evaluate results that are relevant to understanding the extent to which these programmes can make the health services more sustainable. This is also a critical gap when it comes to improve the sustainability and achieve both health related and other sustainability goals (WHO, 2015). To measure and understand how complex health interventions as LHW-programmes work, multiple components can be included and operate through several pathways and have multifaceted effects (Lewin et al., 2017). Evaluation of these interventions therefore needs to include intermediate outcomes – such as self-efficacy

or empowerment – that can elucidate mechanisms of action or the “black box” between implementation and end point impacts (Skivington et al., 2021). Because such outcomes are not always measured, or are measured inconsistently in LHW programme evaluations, it is often not clear why these did or did not improve health outcomes. An outcomes framework can provide a mechanism for examining the pathways between interventions and outcomes. Variations in outcome reporting also make it challenging to compare and analyse the effects of LHW programmes, particularly in systematic reviews. Initiatives such as COMET (Core Outcome Measures in Effectiveness Trials) are attempting to address this gap by developing core sets of outcomes for specific areas of health care in order to promote consistency and congruence in evaluation outcomes (Williamson et al., 2012).

Our proposed core outcome set aims to establish common language for future evaluations and help ensure the selection of appropriate, consistent and comparable outcomes for LHW programmes that include assessment of their contributions to making healthcare more sustainable (Comet-initiativ, 2025).

Objectives

To develop a core outcome set for the evaluation of LHW programmes for diabetes in the context of sustainable healthcare

Research questions

- What outcomes have been assessed to date in evaluations of LHW programmes for chronic conditions?
- What outcomes are critical to assessing the environmental, social and economic impacts of LHW programmes for chronic conditions, and how can these be incorporated into an outcome set for future evaluation and planning of more sustainable healthcare?

The study will be limited to LHW outcomes regarding adults > 18 years of age, living with diabetes. Further limitations are LHWs working with individuals living with diabetes in their own homes, connected to home nursing care or their local society. LHWs connected to hospitals will not be considered.

Method and design

Development of a diabetes core outcome set

Development of a core outcome set (COS) uses multiple methods and takes place in three main steps (Beiderbeck et al., 2021; Harman et al., 2018; Kirkham et al., 2017). Step 1. Defining the scope: specifying the setting, the health condition, the population, and the interventions that the COS will cover. Step 2. Identifying the stakeholders: the patients with the condition, health professionals and those who will use the COS. Step 3: The consensus process: which contains considering the views of the stakeholders using workshops and the Delphi method. Specify criteria for changing or adding new COS, consider use of language towards the different groups of stakeholders to ensure the everyone understands them. In addition to this there is also the analysing process and reporting (Harman et al., 2018; Kirkham et al., 2017). Based on this our project is divided into 6 steps to make the overview of the project easier (see table 1).

Main steps		Timeframe
Step 1 Preparing	Scoping, reading up on articles analysing the systematic review Literature search	8 -6 weeks
	Making the long list of outcomes	
	Invitations and put up a stakeholder group	
Step 2 Workshop	Workshop 1	6 weeks
	Workshop 2	
	Rewrite the long list of outcomes	
Step 3 Delphi rounds	Deciding software and making the Delphi survey	First Delphi round will take place after the results of workshop 2 is ready
	Delphi round 1	
	Analysing result between rounds	
	Delphi round 2	
	Analysing result between rounds	2- 3 weeks between rounds. 2-3 weeks analysing Delphi round 2 and preparing for the consensus meeting
Step 4 Consensus process	Online meeting	
	Analyse results	

Step 5 Analysing	Final analyses	2-6 weeks
Step 6 Reporting	Writing the report	

Table 1. Overview over the different steps in this project and the timeframe

Inclusion and exclusion criteria

Outcomes

Accepted studies must include an LHW intervention for diabetes. Participants must be over 18 years of age. No restrictions in terms of gender, nationality or when the study was conducted.

Exclusions: Studies where the outcomes do not apply to diabetes and/or has diabetes as a comorbidity will be excluded. Data that includes persons under the age of 18 or includes research on their caregivers will be removed.

For sustainability outcomes a literature search will be performed. The articles from this search must include some combinations of the search words diabetes, lay health workers and sustainability/environmental sustainability. Articles that do not include at least a combination of two of the search word will be excluded. Because of limited time there might be set a restriction to five years for when the study was conducted if the search strategy conducts a huge number of articles.

Stakeholders

All stakeholders participating in the Delphi method must be over 18 years of age.

LHW and volunteers from various organizations aimed at health (for example patient organizations such as the Norwegian Diabetes Association, Menighetspleien), Healthcare personnel (E.g. nurses, auxiliary nurses, medical doctors, physiotherapist, occupational therapist), healthcare managers at various organizational levels (E.g. front-line managers close to clinical practice like ward managers; middle managers; top executives such as head of municipal health- and care services), health service researchers.

Individuals living with diabetes or individuals living with multimorbidity where one of the diseases is diabetes, living independently in their own home and with some help at their daily living or with some need of LHW, but with no cognitive impairment.

Exclusion: Patients undergoing hospital treatment at time of inclusion.

The Delphi method

Step 1: Preparing and the Stakeholder group

To identify outcomes regarding LHW for diabetes, data used for a Cochrane systematic review for lay health worker for diabetes from Pantoja et al. (2022) will be used. The systematic review consist of data extractions from randomised trials (RCT) and cluster randomised trials (CRCT) of LHW interventions regarding diabetes (Pantoja et al., 2022).

The trials and data extraction in the systematic review is organized in to different pages to get an overview of the studies characteristics (bibliography, id, study acronym, publication, study date, funding, conflict of interests, clinical trial registration, contact information, area of health and health subgroup, treatment/prevention, study design, number of participants, target population, participant age, participant gender, employment status, geography, health care setting, outcomes measured in study, outcomes measured in time, additional comments), study groups (id, LHW groups, intervention/control, group name, LHW title, gender, delivery mode, task category, intervention duration and frequency, duration, LHW monitoring/supervision, LHW supporting materials, LHW payment, LHW link to health system, number allocated to group), and if the studies have dichotomy or continuous data, and references. Outcomes in this project will be extracted according to inclusion criteria.

The articles from the systematic review and the literature search will be read for familiarizing with the articles and also for looking for any missed information. Drawing on a pragmatic analysis to find patterns and trends will be done for all the extracted data. The outcomes from the systematic review will be extracted, coded using colours for similar themes and made into a list of outcomes.

Stakeholders and participants

The aim is to include as many stakeholders as possible, and hopefully at least five stakeholders in all the mentioned groups with a total of n=25. To provide reliable outcomes

from the workshop a number of eight participants is considered as the lowest total number if the recruitment of stakeholders/participants should prove to be challenging. We will adopt a pragmatic attitude towards the maximum number of participants, and especially for the Delphi rounds (Kirkham et al., 2017). There will be no restrictions to nationality, country, gender or age when it comes to the stakeholders.

There will be five different stakeholder groups:

1. Lay health workers and voluntaries (n =5)
2. Diabetics and/or multimorbid persons (n =5)
3. Health care personnel (E.g. medical doctors, nurses/diabetic nurses and auxiliary nurses) (n= 5)
4. Managers in the health service (E.g. front-line managers close to clinical practice like ward managers; middle managers; top executives such as head of municipal health- and care services) (n =5)
5. Researchers in the field of chronic conditions and from developing core outcome sets. (n =5)

Recruitment of stakeholders and participants

Participants will be recruited via e-mail, asked directly asked directly by project manager either person-to-person meetings, via phone calls, newspaper advertisements or using snowball method.

All the invitees will receive a written invitation via e-mail, in hand or via postal services, to read and familiarize them self with the project. The recruitment will be slightly different for each of the different stakeholder groups. Participants in the LHW/voluntary group will be recruited from voluntary organisations like Norwegian Diabetes Association, Menighetspleien and The National Association for Public Health. Individuals living with diabetes and being a member of such organisations might be recruited there via snowball method. For individuals living with diabetes who get help from the municipal service we will ask the managers in their district to pass on the invitation to patients they see might fit into the inclusion criteria. The patients then may correspond to their nurses, who in turn will pass on answers back to us. If there is difficult to recruit LHWs working with diabetes, LHWs

working in general with chronic diseases will be recruited instead. Health care professionals will basically be recruited via their managers or using the snowball method.

After sending the invitation it is thought that 1-2 weeks is a reasonable period of reflection. If no answer is available after 1 week, a reminder will be sent with an invitation to answer yes or no. If the person in question has still not responded after two weeks, it is assumed that the requested person is not interested in participation. Reminders of answers regarding participation can be sent out by e-mail, with any nurses, telephone or by regular mail.

Step 2: Workshop

With the key stakeholders/participant group we will hold a workshop to present the results from Step 1 (see table 1) and to identify possible new outcomes. The workshop will be led and attended by this doctoral project's supervisors and will be chaired by an experienced researcher from this group.

The workshop will be divided into two days; the first day will be for the LHW, health personnel, health managers and researchers, and day two will be for the individuals living with diabetes. That will make it easier to use language and terms directed to each group to be sure no one misunderstands any of the terms. It might also be easier to speak freely among their own group/kind, instead of being placed with health care professionals or researchers (Jacobsen, 2016). To avoid conformity bias or group dynamic bias (Jacobsen, 2016) and to keep up with the minimum standards of COS development the stakeholders will, preferably, be divided into their own groups during this workshop (Taylor et al., 2017). If few stakeholders are recruited, the groups will be fewer and there will be a mix of the different stakeholders in those groups.

The workshop will begin with introductions of the participants and to introduce the project and the long list of outcomes, and to explain the rationale behind the project and what to do. To prevent losing any new outcomes from the discussion the workshop discussions will be recorded and transcribed. All participants will be informed of this and will be presented both a written and oral consent form. If a participant refuses recording of the meeting, there will be written notes instead.

Step 3: Delphi rounds

After the workshop the existing outcomes and eventually the new outcomes from the workshop will be rewritten into a Delphi survey. We are planning two Delphi rounds and one consensus meeting, but a third Delphi round might apply if there is too many borderline outcomes from Round two. If there is a challenge recruiting enough participants in Step 1, a new round of recruiting stakeholders for the Delphi rounds will need to be done with the same method as explained under Step 1.

For the Delphi rounds we will be using the Welphi platform. Welphi is a computer programme that, among other things, is designed for Delphi surveys (Welphi, 2025). This Delphi survey is made as a six-point Likert scale (Remus et al., 2021) for each question, or outcome. The scale levels are as following: Very important (five points), important (four points), Neither important or unimportant (three points), unimportant (two points), very unimportant (one point) and I Don't know/unsure (zero points). The outcomes will be ranked with a 70% threshold, outcomes rated less than 70% by all the stakeholder groups will not go further to the next round.

The participants may see how the different domains are ranked, but they cannot see who has ranked or what they have ranked (Crew & Williamson). The first round (R1) will be sent out to the stakeholders and other participants after the results from the workshop is finished and reworked. The stakeholders will rank the existing outcomes and be given the opportunity to add new outcomes to the list in R1. Participants will be given approximately two weeks to respond. If no response after five days, a reminder will be dispatched (either via email or as a telephone call). It is estimated that a maximum of two reminders may be issued. Round two (R2) is planned to be sent out 2-3 weeks after R1. In R2 there will be no option of adding new outcomes. After each of the rounds a summary of the result from rounds one is sent out to the stakeholders.

Step 4. Consensus

To have a final agreement of the outcomes, stakeholders from the workshop and the Delphi rounds will be invited to the consensus meeting. The consensus meeting will be chaired by a senior researcher from this doctoral project's supervision group. The consensus meeting will

be held online, but if there is participants not computer literate, or does not have access to a computer, we will open for a mixed meeting where stakeholders can attend either physically or digitally.

Before the meeting the outcomes will be explained in written form and sent out to the participants at least one week before the meeting. The outcome explanations will be written in a plain language to make sure that all participants understand the meaning of each outcome.

At the consensus meeting we will go through each outcome and vote on these. The cutoff for inclusion of the outcomes will be set to 70% (e.g. 70% of consensus meeting participants agree to inclusion) (Kirkham et al., 2017). If there is anything unclear about the agreements of the outcomes, we will consider having two consensus meetings instead of one, to correct and clarify and disagreements.

Step 5: Analyses

This is a mixed method project, and the analyses will therefor mirror this.

For the qualitative data, comments and statements that comes from the discussions from the workshops and the consensus meeting, a pragmatic analysing method will be used. Finding new outcomes from hole sentences and catchwords from the transcribed data. Coding will be done manually.

Descriptive statistics will be used to analyse the results from the Delphi rounds and the consensus meeting. As explained in step 4; outcomes will be regarded valid if there is an 70% agreement from a stakeholder group. If an outcome is ranked less than 70% by all the stakeholder groups it will not continue to the next round. For the consensus meeting all outcomes having a 70% agreement will be considered to the COS.

Step 6: Reporting

Reporting will be done according to Core outcomes Set-Standards for reporting (Kirkham et al., 2016)

Search strategy for literature search

Electronic searches for sustainability outcomes will be made in the database Web of Sciences as this database covers a wide range of subject areas and Core Outcome Measures in Effectiveness Trials (COMET).

Missing data

Missing data, such as skipped items or non-responses, may introduce bias (Jamie J. Kirkham et al., 2019). We will send reminders to non-responders and require all items to be completed; paper surveys will be checked for missing answers and returned to participants for completion.

Ethics

This project is approved by the Norwegian agency for shared services in education and research (SIKT), with reference number: 954611.

For developing core outcomes sets there will be no need to have an approval from an Ethic committee. All participation in this project is voluntary. All stakeholders will receive written information about the study, the information will be given in either English or Norwegian language.

Data collected from stakeholders will be stored on one computer where only one person has access, documents will be marked as strictly confidential. The computer belongs to NTNU. All communication with the stakeholders will be anonymous.

Information provided by stakeholders will be deleted when the interviews have been transcribed and outcomes been extracted. All participants can, with no consequences for themselves, withdraw from the study at any time and their interviews/statements will be deleted, except for data that has already been analysed and possibly published.

The following data is collected from the participants/stakeholders:

- For all stakeholders: information about age, gender, place of residence, education and occupation will be collected

- Individuals living with diabetes: diagnoses, and eventually use of health services/need for assistance
- LHW, health personnel and health managers: work municipality
- Their views on the use of LHW and what may be relevant outcomes

Discussion

A narrow time frame making the long list of outcomes from the systematic review and making a literature search for finding sustainability outcomes may possibly contribute to outcomes being overlooked or not enough time to make properly systematic research for sustainability outcomes. The stakeholder group is tried to keep as diverse as possible, but inviting frail elderly people with diabetes to participate might be a challenge.

Missing data, for example if participants do not answer all the items in the Delphi survey or don't respond at all may also lead to bias (J. J. Kirkham et al., 2019). We will try to counter this by sending participant reminders if they do not respond and also make sure that they can't skip an item when they are answering. For an example they can't send in the survey form if not all items are answered. For participants that require answering in paper form, the form will be checked for missing answers, and the participants will be asked to fill out.

To prevent attrition bias only ranked outcomes and statements or comments made from participants participating in all the Delphi rounds will be considered.

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